

The solid angle of the sky can be observed at night on earth

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Abstract

It is demonstrated that both the sun and the earth are stationary by analyzing the solid angle of the sky that can be observed on the earth. Except the moon, which revolves around the earth, all the other planets revolve around the sun. The sky that can be observed on the earth is only within a solid angle of 0.005 degrees back to the sun. The range of the sky that can be observed on earth is only a very small area compared with the vast universe. Therefore, some stars, including the Big Dipper, can be observed in all seasons on the earth, but their directions and orientations are different.

As long ago as 340 B.C. the Greek philosopher Aristotle thought that the earth was stationary and that the sun, the moon, the planets, and the stars moved in circular orbits around the earth. This idea was elaborated by Ptolemy in the second century A.D. into a complete cosmological model. The earth stood at the center, the sun, the moon, the planets, and the stars move around the earth. There were also fixed stars in the sky, which always stay in the same positions relative to each other but which rotate together across the sky.

After more than a thousand year, a different model was proposed in 1514 by a Polish, Nicholas Copernicus. His idea was that the sun was stationary at the center, and that the earth and the planets moved in circular orbits around the sun. The details of this model are that the earth revolves continuously around its axis once a day and around the sun once a year [1]. With this model the situations can be perfectly explained that the sun rises in the East and sets in the West, and that there is four seasons, spring, summer, autumn, and winter, in one year.

However, the rotations of the fixed stars observed on earth, for example the Big Dipper, change their directions with the change of the four seasons. This phenomenon cannot be explained by heliocentric model. Because in this model the direction of the earth's axis SN keep unchanged and points to the Polaris while it travels around the sun [1].

If we take the earth as a fixed star, it can not only explain the changes of sunrise, sunset and the four seasons, but also reasonably explain the changes in the directions of the Big Dipper with the four seasons [2-4].

In this paper, we demonstrate that both the sun and the earth are stationary by analyzing the solid angle of the sky that can be observed on the earth. As shown in Fig.1, the distance between the earth and the sun is $D=149,597,870\text{km}$, and the radius of the earth is $R_E=6371\text{km}$. So, the solid angle θ of the sky observed on the earth can be calculated as follows,

$$\text{tg}\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) = \frac{R_E}{D} = \frac{6371\text{km}}{149,597,870\text{km}} = 0.00004259$$

$$\theta = 2\text{arctg}\frac{R_E}{D} = 2 \times 0.0025^\circ = 0.005^\circ$$

Figure 1 The solid angle of the sky observed on earth

Because the sun's light is too strong, it can only be observed when the sky is away from the sun. In other words, only the area of sky within the solid angle θ can be observed from the earth, as shown in Fig.2. According to this analysis, the sky seen in mid-spring and mid-summer will not repeat, as shown in Fig.3. Not to mention mid-spring and mid-autumn, mid-summer and mid-winter. This further confirms that the earth does not revolve around the sun.

Figure 2 The area of sky can be observed from earth at night.

Figure 3 Earth position around the Sun in mid-spring and mid-summer.

Therefore, the earth is fixed on the side of the sun, as shown in Fig.4. If we observe the sky on the Tropic of cancer, our position on the earth at midnight in mid-spring is shown in Fig. 4 (a). The position of the Tropic of cancer on the earth at midnight in mid-summer, mid-autumn, and mid-winter are also shown in Fig. 4 (b), (c), and (d). The Tropic of cancer is in the same solid angle where the sky can be observed at midnight in the four seasons, rotating along ellipse A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4 , as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 4 The position of the Tropic of cancer on the earth at midnight in mid-spring (a), mid-summer

(b), mid-autumn (c), and mid-winter (d).

Figure 5 The position of the Tropic of cancer at midnight rotates along ellipse A_1 , A_2 , A_3 , A_4 , in the four seasons.

Because the Tropic of cancer of the earth is in the same solid angle where the sky can be observed at midnight in the four seasons, there are stars, including the Big Dipper, that can be observed in the four seasons. And because the north-pole of the earth is rotating, the stars we see are as if rotating as well. Therefore, the Big Dipper can be seen all the year, and the direction and the orientation of the Big Dipper is different in different seasons.

In summary, both the sun and the earth are all stationary. Except the moon, which revolves around the earth, all the other planets revolve around the sun. The sky that can be observed on the earth is only within a solid angle of 0.005 degrees back to the sun. The range of the sky that can be observed on earth is only a very small area compared with the vast universe. Therefore, some stars, including the Big Dipper, can be observed in all seasons on the earth, but their directions and orientations are different.

References

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